

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D6.2

PROJECT WEBPAGE AND SOCIAL MEDIA REPRESENTATION

Summary:

This document describes the structure and elements of the SUMEX website (www.sumexproject.eu) as well as the project's social media channels. The website serves as a dynamic resource portal and a repository for the project's results and outputs. The social media channels are all directly linked on the website.

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This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The SUMEX social media channels have been set up in early November 2020, timely to promote the project's launch event. At this time, a basic landing page has also been set up, linking all communication channels in one single place.

The professionally designed project website has been launched in January 2021, in month 3 of the project. It includes detailed information about the project's objectives, concept and partners, as well as a newsletter subscription form and links to the social media channels. The website will serve as a dynamic resource portal and a repository for the project's results and outputs. It will be used to provide an overview and continuously publish as much project material as possible, making all intermediate results, reports and other publications accessible for a broad audience.

This document describes the website structure and elements as well as the project's overall social media representation. All electronic communication channels will evolve with time, to ensure the best possible interaction with users during the project's lifetime.

1 SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS

The project's social media channels have been set up in early November 2020 in order to allow for a timely promotion of the SUMEX launch event on 17 November 2020.

The following accounts have been created:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sumex-project>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/SUMEXproject>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/SUMEXproject>
- YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZflrEOO5jiHoZi7MYua0ZA>

All channels are linked in the footer of the project website to invite visitors to follow SUMEX full range of communication tools.

Figure 1: Links to the social media channels in the footer of the SUMEX website.

A YouTube and Twitter feed have also been added to the website's news section to ensure the page is dynamic and provides a complete overview of all ongoing activities.

Figure 2: YouTube and Twitter feed in the news section of the SUMEX website.

Further information about the social media strategy and KPIs is provided in the SUMEX dissemination and communication plan (D6.1).

Social media statistics are gathered on a monthly basis to analyse visitor trends and adapt the communication strategy accordingly.

2 NEWSLETTER

A newsletter subscription form has been set up in December 2020 in order to invite stakeholders who expressed interest in the SUMEX launch event to subscribe and receive all project news directly through the SUMEX channels in the future.

The subscription form is available at the following link:

https://748dd9f9.sibforms.com/serve/MUIEANsM_jIZJhTNJQTy4G6xWPzzLWifdSAEBME8PhFoEcOaZRoR0EysP0YoZrAmnLG_d4o7IZLSCLrKHgp_5GIQEue9aah5gbvbNSDQC5aK5SPX3i5eL7Hin3j8mN62NoGeLXrOOV-6R_RE372t_M9ti96ABDBf8jpijAEuAqmwmnda8wv4FW0_iTRY53KgQD5utXIXIWR1jtzl

Figure 3: Link to the newsletter subscription form on the SUMEX website.

It is foreseen to publish four dedicated SUMEX newsletters (M6, M18, M32, M36). Further details are provided in the dissemination and communication plan (D6.1).

3 PROJECT WEBSITE

The domain name “sumexproject.eu” and a webhosting service have been purchased by EFG in November 2020. The website is hosted by the Icdsoft web hosting service and is managed through a WordPress environment (DIVI theme).

A basic landing page was set up to link all social media channels and promote the launch event on 17 November 2020.

In early November 2020, a call for tenders was launched (*Annex 1*), in order to identify a professional website design company to develop the final design as a sub-contractor. Seven website developer companies have been contacted by personal emails, and the call for tenders was posted at <https://www.freelancer.com>, where many applications were received. The best offer has been received by Leonidas. The company has been in continuous contact with EFG since December. The company first installed the DIVI website builder theme, then created private demo pages. These new pages have been provided to EFG’s communication team for feedback and the final versions have been developed in close collaboration with the project’s coordinating team.

The final version of the project website has been delivered in M3, at the end of January 2021.

3.1. FRONT-END ELEMENTS

3.1.1. NAVIGATION STRUCTURE

The main navigation menu is situated on top of the page and provides access to general information about the project, the case studies, partners, dissemination material and a contact panel.

Figure 4: Main navigation structure of the SUMEX website.

A secondary menu at the bottom of the page also provides access to the news section and the events calendar.

Figure 5: Secondary menu at the bottom of the SUMEX website.

3.1.2 PAGE LAYOUT

The page layout of the SUMEX website is illustrated in the image below. This layout considers the horizontal navigation menu on the upper right side of the screen, an image slider above the text area and a secondary horizontal menu on the bottom of the page. This structure is common to all sub-menus of the website.

Figure 6: Layout of the SUMEX front page.

3.1.3 VISUAL IDENTITY

The general website design is intended to be modern, dynamic and interactive with a clear visual identity. Design and colour choice are adapted to the logo and templates developed by the project team. The visual identity of SUMEX is detailed and established in the project stylebook (D6.1). The website also has a responsive design which means that people can view it on different devices, like mobiles, PCs or tablets.

3.1.4 IMAGES

The website features several graphical illustrations that were all provided by the web design team from Leonnidas.

The website also uses proprietary images or images provided by project partners. These images convey themes aligned with the objectives of SUMEX.

3.1.5 CONTENTS

The information is provided in easy-to-read chunks, optimised for screen dimensions and human vision. The text file of the website content is provided in *Annex 2*.

3.2. BACK-END ELEMENTS

The back-end elements of the SUMEX website were developed to allow the collection of data from visitors and to facilitate the access to the information provided by SUMEX. This means the back-end of the SUMEX website allows the use of polls, subscription forms or statistics collection. The news section of the SUMEX website is also linked to Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter, allowing the instantaneous and synchronous dissemination of information.

3.2.1. CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The SUMEX website has been developed based on a WordPress Content Management System (CMS) because it is easy to use for people who have only limited experience in web publishing and can be updated without having to directly edit the html. The CMS allows for documents to be prepared, edited, approved, and tracked prior to publication, using a working area on the web page that can be easily changed on a regular basis. Clear guidelines on the CMS usage have been provided by the web designers.

To optimise the general operability, the website programming included tests with different browsers and most used devices (Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, Firefox), cookie law adjustment, and SEO settings such as friendly URLs, titles and metatags. The website is flexible and allows future extensions of its functionality as required but always under CMS restrictions.

3.2.2. SITE SEARCH

The website navigation menu includes a search box, allowing visitors to do a simple and fast search on the entire web page contents.

3.2.3. CONTACT FORM

The SUMEX webpage includes a contact form, alongside with an email address that directs the visitor to the project coordinator.

3.2.4. STATISTICS

The WordPress statistical analysis has been set up in November 2020. The visitor statistics are monitored on a monthly basis to analyse visitor trends.

3.3. OTHER COMPONENTS

3.3.1 HOSTING AND CONTENT MANAGEMENT

The SUMEX website is hosted by the Icdsoft web hosting services. Content updates are managed by the European Federation of Geologists.

3.3.2 DOMAIN NAME

The domain name is www.sumexproject.eu.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This document is a live document, despite its delivery date, as details related to website and social media could change during the project time frame. Nevertheless, the general structure and approach will stay stable and will as such offer a solid foundation for the SUMEX project's effective outreach and dissemination activities.

ANNEX 1: CALL FOR TENDERS

Call for web design tenders

The European Federation of Geologists (EFG) invites interested parties to submit a tender for the development of a website within the scope of the EU-funded SUMEX project (grant agreement no: 101003622). The overall design and colour choice should be adapted to the project logo and templates that are currently being developed by the project team and will be provided to the selected tenderer prior to the start of the website development.

The tender shall be based on the terms of reference below and provide a detailed outline of the services offered, a breakdown of the total costs, references to third-party software, products or services the tenderer intends to use and references to similar services provided by the tenderer previously.

Website SUMEX

General information

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the European Commission that has started on 1 November 2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other stakeholders in seizing this opportunity.

In order to foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (Sustainable Management in EXtractive Industries) will establish a framework of what sustainability means for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate (SLO) considerations and will involve stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU. This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states (MS) and selected regions along five focus areas - socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars.

In SUMEX, the experience from other H2020 projects like MINGUIDE, MINLAND, MIREU, RESOURCING, STRADE, INFAC, etc. builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Purpose of the website

The project website shall serve as a dynamic resource portal and a repository for the project's results and outputs. It will be used to provide an overview and continuously publish as much project material as possible, making also intermediate results, survey reports, workshop reports and other publications accessible for a greater audience. The website will also be integrated with communication and dissemination tools that will allow the interaction between project partners and interested parties

participating in the project activities. It will be developed with regular updates for interaction with the audience throughout relevant social media channels.

Requirements

The contractor would be expected to setup a website based on a Content Management System (CMS) that is easy to use for people who have only limited experience in web publishing. Clear guidelines on the CMS usage should be provided. EFG is currently working with a WordPress environment, but we are open to any kind of open-source suggestions.

The general website design should be modern, dynamic and interactive such as www.engieproject.eu, www.crowdthermalproject.eu, www.infactproject.eu, www.eurogeologists.eu, www.spire2030.eu. It should also cover the development of illustrations and design elements in line with the project description. The tenderer is expected to provide a design portfolio and case studies of similar contracts.

The website and CMS should provide the following core features:

- SEO
- Managing texts, articles, images, videos, downloadable files, etc.
- Full-text search engine
- Sitemap
- News section with social media sharing options
- Embedded social media feeds, e.g. Twitter feed
- Events calendar
- About the project page, including
 - Introduction
 - Project objectives
 - Methodology
 - Expected impact
- Partners description, including
 - Project partners
 - Linked third parties
 - Advisory Board members
- Press corner page with
 - New reports
 - Press releases
 - Relevant presentations
 - News section
- Newsletter subscription

The website should be flexible and allow future extension of its functionality, as required. The website shall be launched by **15 January 2021**.

The tenderer is kindly asked to include an optional bid to also host the website, in case the tenderer offers such service.

DELIVERABLE 6.2

Budget

The project foresees an overall budget of 2.500 € for the development of the project website and its various features (excluding web hosting).

Contact

Interested parties are invited to submit their tender to anita.stein@eurogeologists.eu no later than **16 November 2020**, 24:00 CET. Notification of the contract award will be given by 20 November 2020. Do not hesitate to contact us at the same email address for any additional information or queries.

ANNEX 2: SUMEX WEBSITE CONTENT TEXT FILE

- 0- Home page (not in the menu)
- 1- Concept
 - a. Background
 - b. Approach
 - c. Expected Impact
- 2- Team
 - a. Consortium
 - b. Advisory Board
 - c. Linked Third Parties
- 3- Case studies
 - a. Andalusia
 - b. Other regions
 - c. Construction and battery minerals
- 4- toolkit of good practises and principles (2021/2022)
- 5- CoP (2021/2022)
- 6- Press corner
 - a. News section
 - b. Deliverables
 - c. Media information
- 7- Get involved
- 8- Contact

Contents:

- 0. Home page

SUMEX - Sustainable Management in Extractive Industries

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the European Commission that has started on 1 November 2020. The project aims to establish a sustainability framework for the European extractive industry, under the involvement of stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

Latest news about SUMEX

<i>SUMEX project starts!</i>	<i>Launch event</i>
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Learn more about SUMEX's (horizontal icon list)

Concept – Team – Press corner – Get involved

Footer:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 101003622. +EU flag

Events calendar

Newsletter subscriptions

Legal notice (<https://www.sumexproject.eu/legal-notice/>)

Social media:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/SUMEXproject>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sumex-project>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/SUMEXproject>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCZflrEOO5jiHoZi7MYua0ZA>

1. Concept

a. Background

In order to foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (Sustainable Management in EXtractive industries) will establish a **sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe**. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve **stakeholders from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU**.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along **five focus areas - socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration** - to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader **Community of Practice (CoP)** and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant stakeholder groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars.

In SUMEX, the **experience from other projects** like MINGUIDE, MINLAND, MIREU, STRADE builds a

powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

What makes SUMEX stand out?

- It involves **Andalusia as a regional partner** to act as 1) a test case and 2) to involve other regions, i.e. those represented in MIREU and the OECD Mining Regions and Cities Initiative, to participate in SUMEX; as well as having access to the informal network of mining authorities and
- It covers **two practical use cases**, involving industry partners, for two important and completely different raw material groups – **construction** and **battery materials**.

The European Commission is funding SUMEX under the Grant Agreement number 101003622 with € 1 999 551,25 EU contribution.

b. Approach

Definition and operationalisation of sustainable management in the EU context

Despite the broad acceptance of sustainability as a narrative and/or concept for policy development and policy implementation, a broad agreement regarding its operationalisation in the extractive industries in Europe is still contested or even lacking. SUMEX will establish a conceptual framework for sustainable management of mineral resources, in the institutional context of the EU, Member States (MS) and relevant subnational units (i.e. regions). The conceptual framework will be established referring to one of the key sustainability concepts such as DSR approach (or e.g. thematic approach, capital frameworks), in the context of weak or strong sustainability.

Clustering & meta-analysis based on previous and current project results

In the last years, a large number of H2020 projects (and adjoining calls and funding) have addressed various aspects of policy implementation, including land-use planning, socio-environmental impact, health & safety or reporting to support transparent permitting processes. However, currently the results are fragmented, dispersed and lack synthesis. Hence, SUMEX will strongly build on meta research, analysing and synthesising work and results that have been conducted in these projects. This systematic synthesis will also provide a view on the gaps and shortcomings of previous research and fill that gap.

Policy analysis, good practises and use cases

While previous projects have covered the full set of commodity groups (e.g. MINLAND), they have not covered horizontal and vertical policy integration and coordination along the entire value chain, which is of particular importance regarding the upstream and downstream processes for mineral resources. Diverse institutional frameworks on the EU MS and subnational levels are increasing the challenge regarding policy coordination and integration as well as a coherent approach of sustainable mineral resource management in the EU. SUMEX will close this gap through the meta-analysis mentioned above and by conducting an in-depth analysis of 2 selected use-cases, covering 2 very different raw materials, which are of pivotal importance in the EU economic context: (a) battery materials, and (b) construction materials.

Development of a digital toolkit of good practises and principles

The toolkit can be understood as a soft policy tool, providing input for learning and capacity building and thus improving policy making, focussing on the access to deposits and transparent permitting procedures. SUMEX will develop a digital toolkit, working as a central and dynamic knowledge repository of good practises and principles. The knowledge repository will be the basis for learning and capacity building processes in the Community of Practice (CoP), which is envisioned to be self-sustaining beyond SUMEX's duration.

Establishment of a Community of Practice (CoP)

A CoP is a group of actors that is sharing a particular practise. Learning is a social phenomenon, that is integrated in culture, values and practises of a certain community. For those experiential approaches, practise and learning are intertwined, explaining the importance of 'real-world' links, application and consequences of the learning experience. A CoP can exist as long as the members believe they have something to contribute to it, or gain from it. SUMEX will strongly draw on the Learners & Leaders League (3L) approach, establishing a CoP using co-located (physical) and virtual environments of engagement and peer learning, facilitating good practise experiences.

c. Expected impacts

Towards the end of the project:

- A tested and validated definition of sustainable management criteria.
- An expanded knowledge on horizontal and vertical policy integration and coordination, policy mixes and conditions that support agenda setting.
- A toolkit which functions as the core of an active learning and exchange environment for the CoP
- Validated good practises and principles, which contribute to better decision making, decision quality and transparent permitting procedures.

Beyond the project boundaries and project period:

- Establish a CoP that will endure after the official project end, supported by the continuation of the 3L platform.
- Support public and political acceptance of mineral extraction: next to public acceptance, political acceptance is crucial to support mineral activities. SUMEX will contribute to both, by enhancing transparent planning, policy and permitting processes and thus increasing trust, and supporting an improved understanding of agenda setting

Long-term:

- Good practises on health and safety are supporting improved working practises in extractive industry operations.

- One-stop-shop for the best up-to-date practices in the extractive industries with the aim to be regularly updated with the two-way information flow governed by the experts (learning from and contributing to with the experience and/or with the information on gaps).
- A long-term platform for providing tools for the wider public.

2. Team

The strength of our consortium

- Montanuniversität Leoben, Leoben, Austria - <https://bergbau.unileoben.ac.at/en/>
- Öko-Institut E.V. – Institut für angewandte Ökologie, Darmstadt, Germany - <http://www.oeko.de>
- Tallinna Tehnikaukool, Tallinn, Estonia - www.ttu.ee
- Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien, Vienna, Austria - www.wu.ac.at
- Arctic Center, University of Lapland, Rovaniemi, Finland - <https://www.arcticcentre.org/EN>
- Wageningen University, Wageningen, the Netherlands - <http://www.wageningenur.nl/nl.htm>
- European Federation of Geologists (EFG), Brussels, Belgium - www.eurogeologists.eu
- Boliden Mineral Ab, Stockholm, Sweden - www.boliden.com
- Union Européenne des Producteurs de Granulats, Brussels, Belgium - <http://www.uepg.eu/>
- Consejería De Empleo Empresa Y Comercio, Sevilla, Spain - www.juntadeandalucia.es

Linked Third Parties

- Geological Society of Estonia, Estonia - <http://www.egeos.ee/egeos/en/>
- Union of Professionals in Natural, Environmental and Forestry Sciences, Finland - <http://www.ykl.fi/>
- Professional Association of German Geoscientists, Germany - <http://www.geoberuf.de>
- Official Spanish Association of Professional Geologists, Spain - <http://www.icog.es>

Advisory Board members

Tbc

3. Case studies (menu item)

a. Andalusia

Andalusia has a long history of mining many commodities, and whilst not the priority anymore, embraces mining in the present day as well. Although the region is generally positive about mining and metallurgy, the past has not been devoid of mining accidents, and they still influence people's perceptions of the industry today. With its history and present-day challenges, the region is a well-suited test case for SUMEX and given that it is very active in MIREU and the OECD Mining Regions and Cities Initiative is well suited to engage other EU regions to participate in SUMEX's Community of Practice (CoP).

b. Other regions

The SUMEX project aims at covering the whole EU and for achieving its highest input and impact, the focus area is divided into 5 regions where regional peer learning workshops are planned: Northern Europe (coordinated by Finnish colleagues), Southern Europe (coordinated by Spanish colleagues), Eastern Europe (coordinated by Estonian colleagues), Western Europe (coordinated by German colleagues) and Central Europe (coordinated by Austrian colleagues).

c. Construction and battery materials

While construction materials are the most important part of Europe's extractive industry in terms of volume, battery raw materials will play an increasingly important role in the switch to electric vehicles and the energy transition. Due to the low value and high volume of construction materials their extraction is widespread throughout the EU. Battery materials on the other hand are mined in fewer regions of the EU and face very different challenges. Project partners from industry (BOL and UEPG), located in different geographic regions and having partners all across the EU, are contributing their practical knowledge and experience to the mapping and analysis of the use-cases, and play a crucial role in the policy analysis and identification of good practices.

4. toolkit of good practises and principles (2021/2022)
5. CoP (2021/2022)
6. Press corner
 - a. News section
 - b. Deliverables
 - c. Media information
7. Get involved

Please contact us directly at info@sumexproject.eu and follow our newsfeed for the latest developments and events through which you could get involved.

8. Contact (menu item)
 - a. Contact form
 - b. Text:

Coordinating team

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Austria

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- Legal notice: <https://www.sumexproject.eu/legal-notice/>